

CHANGE GEAR, GEAR UP: UNDERSTANDING THE SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT EXPERIENCES OF THE TEACHERS IN THE LAST MILE SCHOOLS

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Change Gear, Gear Up: Understanding the School-Based Management Experiences of the Teachers in the Last Mile Schools

Princess Marynee V. Morga,* Johnny S. Bantulo
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This phenomenological study aimed to understand teachers' School-Based Management experiences in the last-mile schools. This study recorded their challenges, their coping mechanisms, and what learning and insights they can share. Moreover, it involved twenty (20) teachers from the Division of South Cotabato in the T'boli II district located at Barangay Maan, T'boli, South Cotabato, Philippines. They underwent in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) using the validated research instrument. The findings of this study revealed that teachers encountered the challenges of Burdening Pressure, Overwhelming Paperwork, Wavering Confidence, Emerging Passiveness, Occurring Misunderstanding, Varying Loads, Unravelling Authenticity, Lacking Knowledge, and Believing in Competence. In addition, they could cope with it by Uplifting Themselves, Receiving Compliments, Free-flowing Dialogue, Safe-Keeping Documents, Preparing Themselves, Replenishing Environment, Sharing Informal Conversation, and Learning Accountability. Finally, their insights were about Becoming One's Best Version, Having a Compassionate Heart, Stepping out of Comfort Zone, Lagging in Action, Hoping in Sanguinity, Laboring in Bliss, and Thriving Values. Further, the data of this study would contribute meaningfully to understanding the real predicaments of mountain teachers. Likewise, this study would motivate and impact the teachers serving the last-mile schools.

Keywords: *educational management, school-based management, last mile schools, experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, insights, phenomenological study*

Introduction

Education is one of the most essential experiences in human life. It will continue to embrace the changes in whatever age of time. It is common knowledge that innovation and upgrades are part of the story of educational development in all phases of education. Thus, the effective use of School-Based Management (SBM) as an integrative and developmental management paradigm can be considered. Likewise, school management, also called school autonomy or site-based Management, aids in bringing about long-term change in the primary education sector (Llego, 2020; Maca, 2019; Malik, 2018).

Moreover, a qualitative study conducted in Jakarta, Indonesia, showed that implementing School-Based Management improves the country's quality of education and raises community awareness of their responsibilities. In addition, SBM highlights the significance of the school's vision and mission and modifications to the educational system and curriculum programs. The principal organizes by delegating authority and responsibilities to staff (Amon & Bustami, 2021; Garcia & Cerado, 2020; Ghani et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) also used the SBM to evaluate the continuous improvement program in educational institution. Furthermore, SBM is thought to create more effective student learning environments by engaging teachers, parents, and other community stakeholders. Additionally, SBM gives administrators, teachers, students, and parents more say over how the educational process is carried out by entrusting them with making decisions on the budget, hiring, and curriculum (David et al., 2019; Ghani et al., 2020; Llego, 2020).

However, administrative tasks are separate from the staffing patterns in public institutions. It means that teachers are carrying out administrative tasks, a circumstance that, albeit disguised from the view of the standard metrics, can degrade teaching quality. According to some teachers, the workload restricts their teaching time. Individual and situational factors fundamentally influence performance (David et al., 2019; Llego, 2020; Rohma et al., 2020).

In addition, researchers indicated that the experience of high-level stress may negatively affect the teachers' well-being. Besides, it influences instructors to quit and look for employment elsewhere. Therefore, it is crucial to determine the underlying source of this issue so that a quick fix may be suggested. Furthermore, the majority was due to intrinsic factors such as workload, time constraints, classroom management, class size, and the rate of educational change and reform. In addition to that, the decision-making power, physical working conditions, professional autonomy, workplace relationships (colleagues, parents, superiors), and organizational culture, just like the general feeling of the workplace and management style, are some of the factors that affect the teacher's well-being (Harmsen et al., 2018; Smith & Yang, 2017).

Nevertheless, it cannot be disregarded that the Schools Division of South Cotabato has been constantly encouraging institutions to embrace the SBM in all types of schools within the province and take this kind of elevation. Based on my readings, I have yet to come across a parallel study on the setting of last-mile schools. The T'boli District II was one of the districts that did not have a validated school on the SBM level of practice. The thought of it scares the core of every teacher in Barangay Maan area. Everyone understood

the magnitude of work that SBM could bring. However, reality remains constant; it evolves, so teachers must cope with the changes in educational structure.

Furthermore, the implementation of School-Based Management is not a piece of cake. School-based Management is a motion of changing gears and gearing it up to face that tremendous task. It goes out of the shell, discovering every layer of one's being and taking responsibility. Moreover, the researcher has yet to come across the same phenomenon that explores the lofty experiences of teachers of the SBM work in the last-mile schools. Likewise, she had also seen the significance and essence of the journey of stabilizing a system within an institution. Thus, many discoveries need to be made in the quest for school-based Management.

With those mentioned above, the researcher aimed to understand and study the structures of experience and consciousness of the teachers in their School-Based Management (SBM) experiences in the last mile schools.

Research Questions

The study aimed to understand how teachers change gear and gear up based on their school-based management experiences in last-mile schools. This study specifically sought to respond to the following questions:

1. How do teachers describe their School-Based Management (SBM) experiences in the last mile schools?
 - 1.1 How do teachers describe the challenges in doing the School-Based Management (SBM) journey in the last mile schools?
 - 1.2 How do teachers describe their coping mechanisms for navigating the School-Based Management (SBM) journey in last-mile schools?
 - 1.3 What insights can the teachers share with others about their School-Based Management (SBM) journey in the last mile schools?

Methodology

This section presents the research design, the role of the researcher, research participants, data collection, data analysis, trustworthiness, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

In this research, the qualitative phenomenological method was employed. The researcher went to a particular setting of interest to collect the data, to describe the natural setting of the direct source of data, and the researcher as well as the key instrument. The goal of the study was to gather data, such as interview transcripts, field notes, audio recordings, diaries, personal comments, official records, or anything else that could capture the actual words or deeds of the study's subjects; thus, this research method was used (Fitchett & Heafner, 2017).

Additionally, as the primary study's main goal was to understand how people interpret their lives, according to Miller et al. (2018), the qualitative research design was suited to employ such a goal. The researcher's focus was the participants' assumptions, motives, reasons, goals, and values about the experiences they encountered in their journey. With that, the researcher tried to capture the thinking of the participants' perspectives as accurately as possible. Moreover, Leavy (2017) affirmed that descriptive qualitative design focused on describing special or essential events as experienced by the teachers participating in their SBM experiences, and these experiences of the participants were noted and recorded. In this study, aside from collecting the unique or essential events the teachers experienced in their journey, the researcher investigated these experiences' various reactions to or perceptions of a particular phenomenon where she hoped to gain some insight from their quest.

In qualitative research, Alam (2021) stated that researchers can use the "what" question to form the research questions. Additionally, it might investigate the "what" as well as the "why" and "how" of a phenomenon in a more comprehensive, detailed, and wide-ranging manner. Further, while it occasionally uses images, videos, or other conduct records, qualitative research frequently uses language as its data, whether written or spoken. The focus group method, interviews, or observations are frequently used to gather qualitative data. The goal of qualitative research is to illuminate the viewpoints of the participants or patients who are the topic of the study. It uses an iterative procedure called "emergent design," which combines data analysis, preliminary data inspection, and data collection (Haven & Van Grootel, 2019).

In summary, the researcher mainly focused on the essential structure of a single phenomenon (experiences of teachers and their School-Based Management journey) by interviewing in-depth and Focusing group discussion. Several individuals who had experienced this phenomenon served as participants in the study. Then extracted what was considered to be relevant statements for each subject's description of the phenomenon and then clustered these statements into themes. The researcher then integrated these themes into a narrative description of the phenomenon. Lastly, these experiences were clustered into emergent themes of experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights from the informants.

Participants

This study used purposive sampling to identify my participants. The researcher purposely included at least twenty (20) participants

who have experienced in School-Based Management. The participants came from six last-mile schools of Barangay Maan in Tboli, South Cotabato. These participants were teachers who have experience in SBM undertakings and who have served the Department of Education for at least three years or more. Additionally, in-depth interviews with the 10 participants were conducted, and the FGD was divided into two sessions with five participants each, consisting of nine females and one man. They were all chosen in the same manner as the informants and were all from the same area. The teaching experiences of the focus group participants ranged from three to five years. The discussions were conducted to gain additional insights into the SBM journey of teachers in the last mile schools and to strengthen and confirm the findings. During the discussion, the participants' real names were not used to protect their identities. They were also assigned pseudonyms. Furthermore, most in-depth interviews were done on the premises of the participants' houses. Moreover, some were conducted in the four corners of their classrooms. In contrast, the Focus Group Discussions were conducted in their schools. According to Adams (2017), the focus group approach is assembling a group of participants to talk about a topic to learn what participants believe about the topic, how they think about it, and why they think the way they do.

Data Collection

Data collection started by identifying the problem or phenomenon of interest, determining the research objective, and collecting the participant's experiences. First, I submitted a Protocol Application to the Ethics Review Committee. Upon approval, I sought the Graduate School Dean's permission to conduct my research study. Then, I communicated my goals and intentions through letters to the Department of Education Schools Division of South Cotabato superintendent, and the school heads followed. Further, the letter to the key informants and informed consent were given, and all the terms and conditions applicable to their participation were explained.

Furthermore, this study followed steps to get the required data. With this, In-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGD) were conducted with the participants to record notes. Ethics was taken into account before the interview was conducted. According to Arfin (2018), in every research project, it is crucial to protect human subjects by putting the proper ethical standards into practice. It balances the ethical issues of research and its expected benefits.

In-depth interviews were one strategy used to gather information from research informants. The in-depth interview technique depicts the participant's viewpoint on the research issue. Further, DeJonckheere and Vaughn (2019) stated that In-depth interviews are the most frequently utilized qualitative data source in health services research and are frequently employed in qualitative research. This method often involves a discussion between the researcher and the participant, facilitated by a flexible interview style and strengthened by follow-up questions, requests for further information, and comments. The method enables the researcher to collect unstructured data, explore participants' thoughts, feelings, and views about a particular topic, and delve deeply into delicate and occasionally private issues.

Moreover, according to Creswell and Creswell (2017), if phenomenological methods are used in qualitative research, it is advised that researchers conduct in-depth interviews with 5–25 individuals who have participated in the same phenomenon if one wants to accomplish the objective of using the criteria of representativeness and generalizability, a modest number of research subjects.

Furthermore, I understood that it was crucial to give the participant a safe and comfortable environment for sharing personal experiences; a comfortable and welcoming atmosphere invites and encourages the participants to converse and share personal information and experiences. It shows that language and environment are key issues that impact the participant's feeling of safety, as Novek and Wilkins (2019) stated. Along with this recommendation, I ensured the interview would be conducted in a quiet place to provide privacy and avoid distractions. The interviews took place in a convenient place that the participants preferred. Most of the in-depth interviews were conducted on the premises of the participants' houses, and some were conducted in the four corners of their classrooms.

On the other hand, the same principle was used in Focus Group Discussion (FGD). According to Morgan (2018), the focus group approach is assembling a group of participants to talk about a topic to learn what participants believe about it, how they think about it, and why they think the way they do. Additionally, Adams (2017) affirmed that focus groups resemble interviews. However, in focus group talks, a focus group's strengths and limitations stem from its two distinguishing characteristics: the reliance on the researcher's emphasis and the group's involvement. Therefore, to do this, I focused entirely on the subjects during the FGD, taking in every detail as they described their experiences and refraining from offering my viewpoint or objecting to the comments made by the participants. I made sure there were no interruptions or noises that could distract from the conversation.

According to Varpio and McCarthy (2017), an interviewer must be sensitive to the reactions and moods of the interviewees. They may occasionally be able to manage these feelings independently. However, other times, as the interviewer, you may need to intervene to safeguard your subject. Moreover, Note-taking should be used to make sure that all material is thoroughly captured and that no significant detail is omitted. Ince audio or video recording enhanced the accuracy of the information revealed in the focus group or in-depth interview, as well as the speaker's intonations, data were gathered through audio recordings of interviews (Huang, 2021).

In addition, the interview's audio tapes were verbatim transcribed, and the participants approved the accuracy of the transcription. All sessions and interactions with all informants were conducted in strict confidence. Quantitative and qualitative researchers are concerned with preserving the privacy and safety of research participants. According to Kirilova and Karcher (2017), providing them with a safe and comfortable environment to share their experiences is vital. In addition, to strengthen trust and confidence, all the tapes recorded

were played for them. If there were issues they wanted to delete, then action should be taken. Further, the notes recorded were shown to them for scrutiny and affirmation.

Furthermore, Surmiak (2018) encouraged using pseudonyms to conceal the participant's identity. For that reason, this study employed that method. Also, I prepared my open-ended research questions as listed in the interview guide to maintain a smooth flow during the in-depth interview. I also let the interviewees know I may have additional questions besides the interview guide as part of probing. They were necessary for gaining additional information for the study; it encouraged openness and trust among the participants.

During data collection, I saw that the principles of listening were observed. This data collection allowed the participants to unveil their feelings, especially those working alone in the assigned SBM principle. I tried to show them that I was with them throughout the time they told their experiences in the SBM journey. It is unavoidable that during their revelation, some issues needed clarification. However, when these were asked again, it was done respectfully to win the participants' trust.

Withal, I saw to it that they signed the certificate of consent and that all the equipment, such as audio tapes, phone recorders, and pen audio recorders as backup, was used with the assurance that everything that happened during the interview and group discussions was held in anonymity. In addition, McGrath et al. (2019) saw the importance of needing ethical approval in whatever form, from the convenient place to conduct the interviews throughout the recorded interview.

As the researcher, I focused on my field of interest (phenomenon) with confidence and trust. I had the necessary knowledge and skills to conduct interviews, group discussions, and note-taking. The objective of conducting this research was a success. With the respect I showed my participants, they cooperated and fully supported this work.

Analysis of Data

The analysis came after the collection of every piece of data needed. The study employed thematic analysis to categorize all the data acquired to comprehend it better. With that, I sought the assistance of an independent data analyst. Data analysis is one of the most significant components of qualitative research. A thorough procedure helps enlighten the complexity of human conduct and inform interventions, leading to hearing the voices of people's lived experiences (Raskind et al., 2019).

In addition, as stated, thematic analysis was used to identify the themes and patterns in the gathered qualitative data. The study used and followed the six-phase guides of Braun & Clarke (2006), as cited by Maguire and Delahunt (2017). It was a valuable framework for conducting this analysis. These included getting to know the data, developing preliminary codes, looking for themes, going over, clarifying, and documenting them.

Data transcription must be done before proceeding to the first stage of the process. I sought help transcribing my data while translating it. I then went on to the first phase, reviewing and rereading the data to familiarize myself. The data taken from the participants were combinations of Tagalog and Cebuano dialects, as well as some English terms.

Furthermore, in generating codes, I asked for help from an independent data analyst to meaningfully and methodically organize our data. Coding compresses a large amount of information to digestible meaning. There are various ways of coding. Thus, the strategy would depend on your viewpoint and study objectives. We discussed the relevant ideas for the research questions. We talked about them and came up with some early concepts for codes. Then, we each started separately coding a transcript. Every passage of text that was pertinent to or mainly addressed our study issue was coded as we went through each transcript. After we were done, we compared our codes, spoke about them, and made changes before going on to the remaining transcripts.

After that, we proceeded to search for themes. Then, we looked at the codes in this instance; some made up a theme. The themes derived described trends in the data that were important to the research questions. The next stage is reviewing the themes by modifying and developing the initial themes and investigating if they are helpful and relevant. We examined each theme's corresponding data and evaluated whether the evidence supported it. It was considered whether the themes made sense when seen in the context of the complete data set at the following stage.

Moreover, the final refinement of the themes followed the fifth stage, which was to define themes. Considering the following questions, what was the theme trying to say? If there were sub-themes, how did they relate to and interact with the central theme? What connections were there between the themes? These were the necessary steps I took to analyze the data gathered.

Results

This section presented the findings of the study based on the gathered data taken from the participants.

6.1 Participants

This study had twenty key informants, sixteen women, and four men. These teachers serve the sitio schools at Barangay Maan, Municipality of T'boli, also known as T'boli II District in the Division of South Cotabato. Their teaching experiences ranged from three years to seven years. They were selected based on their experiences in the School-Based Management journey. The experiences and narration of these teachers were heard, observed, and written, whether pleasant, joyful, painful, or fearful; the stories of teachers,

like the support they received from their colleagues, their hopes and dreams as teachers, and the insights they could share with other teachers. For purposes of confidentiality, the participants were given pseudonyms.

The in-depth interview was conducted with three males and seven females. To begin with, my first informant is a teacher, Abby. She is 31 years old and a teacher at Datal Tablo Integrated School. She has been serving DepEd for four years now. On the other hand, Teacher Bella is a 28-year-old teacher currently serving at Coong Elementary School and is in her fifth year of service. Further, another fellow from a last-mile school happily accepted the chance to be part of this research Teacher Clint, a 28-year-old educator serving Balnabo Elementary School for four years.

Moreover, another teacher from Datal Tablo Integrated School participated in the interview. She is Teacher Debby who is 29 years old and has served her station for four years. Another participant from Balnabo Elementary School contributed to the data collection is 29-year-old Teacher, Eli, who has been in the service for five years. Furthermore, Teacher Franz is a 29-year-old male teacher at Coong Elementary School. He has been in that school for four years.

Additionally, Teacher Gem is a 31-year-old teacher assigned to the farthest schools in the barangay, namely, Lamdamay Elementary School. She has been fervently giving her service for four years. Furthermore, Teacher Hans, a 28 male teacher from Begue Integrated School, purposefully participated in the interview. He has been serving his station for three years. Likewise, Teacher Iris, a 28-year-old educator, has served the Begue Integrated School for four years. Lastly, Teacher Jin, a 31-year-old female teacher from Lamdamay Elementary School, also participated in the data collection for this study. She has been serving the farthest school for five years.

Two focus group discussions were conducted with five participants per FGD, nine females and one male. All of them were from the same locale and were selected in the same way as the informants. The teaching experiences of the focus group participants ranged from three to five years. The discussion was conducted to gain additional insights and constructs on the SBM journey of teachers from the last mile schools and to strengthen and confirm the findings. In order to conceal the true identity of the participants, the use of the participants' real names during the discussion was avoided. They were given pseudonyms as well.

Both study groups answered the same set of questions. The first few participants selected were my acquaintances. Thus, during our get-together, I learned that our experiences in the SBM validation were similar. Purposive sampling was the sampling strategy employed, and through their recommendations and referrals, I could locate additional informants. I arranged meetings with the recommended informants and participants with the help of their school heads and my colleagues. Their lending hands helped me collect data and information.

The first focus group discussion group was the Datal Calon Elementary School teachers. It consisted of five enthusiastic informants. Teacher Kara is 27 years old and has served the school for four years. Teacher Lisa is 34 years old and has been successfully serving the school for three years. Similarly, Teacher Mona is 34 years old and has been at that station for four years. Further, the last participant for the FGD on this particular station is Teacher Oli. She is 29 years of age and has been in school for four years.

Secondly, the following participants for the Focus Group Discussion came from Datal Tablo Integrated School. The data collection was taken from five brilliant and bright informants consisting of one male and four females. Teacher Pearl is a 30-year-old teacher who has been teaching for three years. Further, Teacher Queeny is a 28-year-old teacher whose service has reached four years. Likewise, Teacher Rose has served the institution for four years. She is a 30 year old female teacher. Similarly, Teacher Sara has rendered four years of service. She is a 31-year-old enthusiastic educator. Further, the last informant was the only male in the group, a 28-year-old teacher named Tom, who has also served the school for four years.

Notably, these participants were associated with my friends. That is why I eventually got much help from them, which made my connection with the target informants manageable. This action-built trust, which was deemed significant in extracting their personal information, and they genuinely shared their SBM experiences and journeys. All informants in the in-depth interview were my friends, but some participants in the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were referred to me. Though some were initially anxious, they eventually felt comfortable with my assurance of confidentiality. They were very cooperative in answering each of my interview questions. Through their voice and facial expressions, one could still feel their joy and sadness because of their experiences with the school-Based Management validation.

In addition, the focus group discussion was fascinating, and the interaction was spontaneous. You could hear, in their low voices, how they reacted to the experiences of the other participants. Some had similar experiences, but each had his/her own exciting story to tell of their difficulties and takeaways from that quest.

The interviews took place in different places, depending on the participants' preferences. Some were interviewed in a quiet area of their school campus, or in their humble abode, in the four corners of their classroom, and for the FGD, I went to their schools and interviewed in the actual premise of their SBM room in their schools. Moreover, I saw to it that they signed the certificate of consent and that all the equipment like audio tapes, recorder of my phone, and pen audio recorders as backup were used with the assurance that everything that happened during the interview and group discussions would be held in anonymity.

6.2 Challenges of the Teachers in School-Based Management (SBM) Journey

From the data collected on the challenges encountered by the study participants, nine emergent themes appeared, as presented in Table 1. These themes are Burdening Pressure, Overwhelming Paperwork, Wavering Confidence, Emerging Passiveness, Occurring Misunderstanding, Varying Loads, Unraveling Authenticity, Lacking of Knowledge, and Believing in Competence.

Table 1. *Challenges of the Teachers in SBM Journey*

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Worried and pressured in the task	Burdening Pressure
Retrieval of documents from 3 years back	
Additional tasks to work	
Expectations in achieving Level 3	Overwhelming Paperwork
Never-ending paperwork	
Additional work for teachers	
There are tons of files to accomplish	Wavering Confidence
Lack of guidance	
First time to be evaluated	
Lack of experiences	Emerging Passiveness
They are not performing the task	
Lack of manpower	
Different work ethics	Occuring Misunderstanding
Occurrence of misunderstanding among teachers	
Misinterpretation of instructions	
Resentment among teachers	Varying Loads
Unequal task distribution	
The given task is based on teacher's competence	
Difference work pacing	Unraveling Authenticity
Fabrication of documents	
Lack of Means of Verification	
Lack of supporting documents	Lacking Knowledge
Difficulty in figuring out the task	
Dfficulty is supporting verbal explanation	
Lack of Technical Assistance	Believing in Competence
Belief in their abilities	
Colleagues are competitive	
Everyone has strength and potential	

6.2.1 Burdening Pressure

Responses to the questions asked about the School-Based Management experiences of the teachers in the last mile schools, revealed that burdening pressure is what they feel hearing the notion of SBM and likewise when a certain school shall undergo the SBM validation. Some teachers felt pressured for lacking any idea about it. Similarly, the lack of experience has added the worries for them.

6.2.2 Overwhelming Paperwork

Teachers had their takes when they learned that their school would undergo the SBM validation. But the major feelings and thoughts surfaced about the mountain of additional paperwork to work on. In addition, many documents were needed to be looked at and collected which would add another work for teachers.

6.2.3 Wavering Confidence

Teacher participants were not that confident about their SBM practice in their respective schools. Most of the sitio schools were considered newbie about it. Most of the teachers were not equipped to do the practice of SBM moreover; some schools are newly established.

6.2.4 Emerging Passiveness

One notable problem encountered by the teacher participants was the idleness or passiveness of some colleagues. The feeling of frustrations was evident as they relayed how they combat existing reality within the teaching force.

6.2.5 Occurring Misunderstanding

Conflict is normal in a relationship. Teachers who underwent the journey of SBM validation have experienced some friction along their quest. The pressure and stress encountered normally fueled the misunderstanding and bickering they had come across with.

6.2.6 Varying Loads

The varying loads were normally to the competence of the teachers. These have put some teachers in a tough situation, in doing more compared to others. It was apparent that the workloads were not distributed equally. Some teachers ended up working more on other tasks and covering for others.

6.2.7 Unraveling Authenticity

The legitimacy of data was one of the hardest parts to comply with in the SBM journey. Since most last mile schools are not equipped in following the standard system of the School-Based Management in gathering the data. Teacher participants shared the same agony when it comes to finding and providing authentic documents.

6.2.8 Lacking Knowledge

It was an extra challenge for the last mile schools that not everyone is equipped to do School-Based Management. In general, schools from far-flung areas do not always have the spotlight and standardization that urban schools have. The serving teachers of these sitio schools were more focused on their teaching inside their classrooms. This shows that most of them lack the knowledge when it comes to School-Based Management.

6.2.9 Believing in Competence

The participants had gone through a lot on this SBM journey, nevertheless, most of them had faith in the capabilities of their co-workers. On the edge of toughness, they still managed to see the competence of their teaching force. Most teachers had confidence big or small in their teaching force despite the disadvantages they have experienced.

6.3 Coping Mechanisms of the Teachers in Doing School-Based Management (SBM) Journey

Table 2: Coping Mechanisms of the Teachers in SBM Journey

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
We can achieve level 3	Uplifting Oneself
We will not give up	
No retreat, no surrender	
Colleagues appropriate the task done.	
Hearing works of thanks.	Receiving Compliments
Affirming a job well done.	
There are tons of files to accomplish	Free flowing Dialogue
Brainstorming about SBM with colleagues.	
Communicate clearly.	
Planning the task carefully.	
Intensify school and community communication	Safe keeping of Documents.
Save and secure evidence.	
Secure and print documents.	
Document every activity.	Preparing Oneself
Focus on the given task	
Be familiar with the assigned task	
Review the documents.	
Prepare school environment.	Replenishing Environment
Maintain school cleanliness.	
Improve physical environment.	Sharing Informal Conversation
Integrate SBM tasks on daily activities.	
Informal interaction with colleagues.	
Cross-checking accomplished documents.	Learning Accountability
Provide means of verification.	
Be responsible for the tasks given.	
Perform task accordingly.	

From the data collected on how teachers cope with the challenges while doing the School-Based Management endeavor; eight emergent themes appeared as presented in Table 2. These themes are; Uplifting Oneself, Receiving Compliments, Free-flowing Dialogue, Safe-Keeping of Documents, Preparing Oneself, Replenishing Environment, Sharing Informal Conversation and Learning Accountability.

1.1.1 Uplifting Oneself

Every one of us has a tagline in boosting ourselves in face of difficulties. The participants have been chanting their personal mantra every time they wanted to give up on this SBM endeavor. In addition, words that affirm them are like oil that fuels them to continue and serves a comfort that inspires them to hold on until the validation day. (Most of the teachers have similar taglines, that is, “to fight

because they can do it”.)

1.1.2 Receiving Compliments

On the other hand, the affirmations that brought warmth to the participants were the words “thank you” and “Good Job”. Giving thanks and saying “good job” fuelled the spirit of the teachers. These simple gestures of affirmation also gave an impact to their journey.

1.1.3 Free-flowing Dialogue

For each conflict communication is always the key in solving matters. Similarly, open communication is also effective, especially in dealing with the occurring problems in the endeavor of doing School-Based Management. In open communication, the dilemma would be addressed, the burden would be shared and the solution would be efficient not only for teachers but also for all stakeholders involved in SBM.

6.3.4 Safe-keeping of Documents

The importance of securing the data and MOVs resurfaced as one of the effective ways of coping with the massive tasks that SBM has. Teachers learned that putting effort into safe-keeping documents helps a lot. Securing the documents was necessary to acquire authentic evidence.

6.3.5 Preparing Oneself

There are different faces of preparation, depending on one’s preferences. Doing the School-Based Management has opened the doors to self-assessment. Teachers became keen on arming themselves in preparation for that scheduled day of validation.

6.3.6 Replenishing Environment

The Learning Environment is a big factor in setting the mood of the validators. It showcases that a school is conducive to learning. Undergoing School-Based Management validation is presenting your school as best as it could be. Teachers have seen the importance of making sure that the school environment was not overlooked apart from the documents.

6.3.7 Sharing Informal Conversation

The journey of coping with School-Based Management may come in different ways and shapes. It may be in a formal or informal set-up, as long as there are interactions and discussions related to SBM there is learning. After all, everything that is related to a school is already part of School-Based Management. Most of the time, the teaching force inserted brief updates regarding SBM in their meetings or Teacher’s Conferences.

6.3.8 Learning Accountability

Accountability is also known as taking responsibility for the assigned task given to a person. One person realizes the importance of its essence through experiences. Moreover, the learning and realization gained from it, resulted in growth, maturity, and a better version of oneself.

1.2 Insights that the teachers can share about SBM journey

From the data collected on the insights that the teachers can share with others about their SBM experience; seven emergent themes appeared. These themes are; Becoming One’s Best Version, Having a Compassionate Heart, Stepping out of Comfort Zone, Laging in Action, Hoping in Sanguinity, Laboring Bliss, and Thriving Values.

Table 3: Insights that the Teachers can share about

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Strengthened responsibility.	Becoming One’s Best Version
Surpass the challenges.	
Make things possible.	
Patience and consideration.	Having a Compassionate Heart
Extended understanding and effort.	
Learn to control the uttered words.	
Learn to submit to authority.	
Learn to manage pressure.	Stepping out of Comfort Zone
Embrace personality differences.	
Overcome difficulties and challenges.	
Avoid passive behavior.	Laging in Action
Negligence of task,	
Do not be distracted.	Hoping in Sanguinity
Expectations for a good result	

Self fulfillment on doing the task.	
Embrace positivity.	
Hard work is paid off.	
Overwhelmed feelings.	Laboring in Bliss
Happy for the high score.	
Self discipline and determination.	
Be responsible for the task give.	
Be courageous and optimistic.	Thriving Values
Stick to the guidelines given.	
Stck on the guidelines given.	

6.4.1 Becoming One's Best Version

Self-actualization is the peak of Maslow's hierarchy of needs. Teacher participants admittedly that they leveled up after the School-Based Management validation. They have gained and changed considerably on this journey. It was a quest to rediscover one's self and light a spark of best versions of themselves.

6.4.2 Having Compassionate Heart

The School-Based Management put teachers in situations where they have to exert more patience and understanding to the situation. Their patience was tested and extended in this journey.

6.4.3 Stepping out of Comfort Zone

Conceptually the term geared up refers to the preparation for an activity or event. If a person is geared up to do a particular activity, that someone is prepared to do it. And with that, it means that there is an improvement along the journey. It gave teachers learning personally, interpersonally, and professionally. Many realizations and gearing up happened throughout this undertaking.

6.4.4 Lagging in Action.

Learning is learning whether it is bad or good. Averse to activity or exertion is a nemesis on this journey. Thus, it may paralyze and sometimes can leave a sour taste in the relationship among people. Teachers gave caution on being sluggish when the school is on the track for the SBM validation.

6.4.5 Hoping in Sangunity

The School-Based Management journey of the teachers from the last mile schools resulted in celebration. It was a blast. It was less expected that all far-flung schools would manage to reach Level 3 but they did. Teachers received a good outcome from it, as they reflected on the lens of their hardships and perseverance.

6.4.6 Laboring in Bliss

Overwhelming happiness after the fruit of labor was tasted. All the efforts paid off. That feeling of bliss was evident and manifested at the time that the result was announced. Candidly, it was a moment that made the teachers realize that even the last-mile schools can make it with the right determination and drive. Overflowing emotion of happiness was shared at the time that the teachers recalled that momentous moment of hearing the result of their SBM validation.

6.4.7 Thriving Values

The values that always prove their worth when it is used. These are time-tested weaponry that could lead someone to obtain the desired goal. These are executed unknowingly because these are capacities buried in every one of us. Relatively, doing your part helped a lot and exuded a sense of responsibility for some teachers. Moreover, keeping the positivity alive is a mood setter. In the same manner, patience played an important part in making the journey a success. Furthermore, perseverance, cooperation and working early were also absolute formula in making everything work; apparently these values had kept the teachers from giving up.

6.5 Chapter Summary

The following data were identified based on the responses of the in-depth interview informants and the FGD participants.

Regarding the participants' challenges, nine emergent themes appeared to describe the circumstances encountered by the teacher participants on their school-based management journey. These Emergent themes are Burdening Pressure, Overwhelming Paperwork, Wavering Confidence, Emerging Passiveness, Occurring Misunderstanding, Varying Loads, Unraveling Authenticity, Lacking of Knowledge, and Believing in Competence. Concerning pressure, the responses revealed that burdening pressure is what they feel hearing the notion of SBM and when a particular school undergoes the SBM validation. Some teachers felt pressured for lacking the idea about it, likewise the lack of documents. Moreover, pressure came from the validation day's time frame and the teachers' expectations. In the context of paperwork, teachers had their takes when they learned that their school would undergo the SBM

validation. Nevertheless, significant feelings and thoughts surfaced about the mountain of additional paperwork to work on.

Eight emergent themes emerged in the participant's responses to the challenges encountered: Uplifting Oneself, Receiving Compliments, Free-flowing Dialogue, Safe-Keeping the Documents, Preparing Oneself, Replenishing the Environment, Sharing Informal Conversation, and Learning Accountability.

Furthermore, participants chanted their mantra whenever they felt like giving up, always fighting because they believed they could. Additionally, receiving compliments encouraged the participants to work. The affirmations that brought excitement to the participants were the words "thank you" and "Good Job". On the other hand, free-flowing dialogue was an inevitable realization for the participants in solving conflict matters. Another urgent realization was the practice of safekeeping the documents because securing the documents was necessary to acquire authentic evidence.

It was equally important to put effort into preparation. There are different faces of preparation, depending on one's preferences. Likewise, replenishing the school environment was also a priority since the learning environment depicts the school's conduciveness. As a team, participants coped in different ways and shapes. It may be in a formal or informal set-up; as long as there were interactions and discussions related to SBM, there was learning and progress. Moreover, finally, being accountable for one's task was vital along the journey.

Seven emergent themes emerged from the insights shared by the participants: Becoming One's Best Version, Having a Compassionate Heart, Stepping out of Comfort Zone, Lagging in Action, Hoping in Sanguinity, Laboring in Bliss, and Thriving Values. The teacher participants admitted that they had improved and leveled up because it was a quest to rediscover themselves and light a spark of new versions of themselves. Similarly, SBM made teachers extend more patience and understanding to the situation and people.

In addition, the improvement that manifested in the informants was seen as they stepped out of their comfort zone. Teachers learned personally, interpersonally, and professionally. Many realizations and gearing up happened throughout this undertaking. However, caution also came from them, such as lagging in action. In other words, passiveness was a nemesis on this journey. This paralyzed and sometimes could leave a sour taste in people's relationships, as per experience.

Eventually, after all the hardships, a Hope in Sanguinity manifested. Overwhelming happiness unfolded after the fruit of labor was tasted. All the effort had paid off. That Laboring Bliss was evident and manifested when the result was announced. Indeed, these were all possible with all the Thriving Values executed by the participants as the School-Based Management journey progressed.

Discussion

This section presents the discussion, implications for practice, and implications for future research based on the themes developed during the data analysis.

With a clear indication, this study aimed to understand the School-Based Management experiences of the teachers in the last mile schools. It aimed to unravel the feelings and insights the participants came across from the beginning to the SBM validation. The outcome of this study would pave the way to a deeper understanding and reflection of how teachers from the last mile schools cope up with the changes in educational structure. Moreover, it sought to go deeper into the issue's core from the experiences of participants and insights that may determine what concepts and themes from the findings.

In exploring and building the participant's experiences, the researcher believed that phenomenology is a powerful research strategy that was well suited for it. Moreover, Merriam and Grenier (2019) stated that for this qualitative research design, the lived experiences about the event or events experienced by the participants during in-depth interviews were recorded and, with the survey questionnaire, were put out and put together, sorted and categorized into different themes. The commonality of the stories told was structured and classified for easy analysis for a common understanding.

Conclusion

They say that a teacher should keep bringing the light, whether in a mountain or a city. Indeed, there is a distinguished joy in mountain teachers like us; I am proud to witness the journey of my informants who accepted the challenge to change gear and gear up, to dance the tango of the School-Based Management journey. Teachers from last-mile schools have been subtly dodging the SBM task. The thought scares every teacher's core since an undeniable workload and responsibility knocks before them. Moreover, SBM is like massive entropy that rushes when one takes the challenge of embracing it.

The experiences of burdening pressure and additional workload are a starting pack at the beginning of the journey. In addition, the majority of the teachers need to gain Knowledge of how it works. Indeed, doubts and hesitation were evident. These led to some stories of bickering and misunderstanding, which affected the relationship of the teaching force. It created an environment that made some teachers idle and dependent on colleagues they deemed competent to do more excellent work.

Relatedly, as a researcher who experienced the difficulty of this journey, I could attest that these problems were real and tangible. However, just like an infamous quote says, 'What does not kill you makes you stronger' has proven that we always find the strength to fight back while breaking. Despite all of the disadvantages and hesitations, there lies a chink of positive aspect in the confidence that

the faith in the teaching force does not wane.

Unarguably, School-Based Management has taken something from us but has given us dramatic growth. The journey has reminded the teachers of their calling in the holistic context. Further, far-flung schools usually do not pursue the standard perceived by urbanized schools; however, this quest revealed that last-mile schools can reach level 3 of SBM practice. This result has astonished everyone: spectators, validators, and teachers.

Subsequently, this may encourage policymakers to uphold a program that aims to improve the intensive upskilling of mountain teachers, hopefully to keep up with urbanized schools. Additionally, with continued enthusiasm for making School-Based Management functional, all stakeholders will be encouraged to work hand in hand with the institutions. This enthusiasm may lead to more opportunities and linkages that would benefit the schools.

Even more, the culmination of this pursuit is the gearing up of these teacher participants. Many realizations and changing gears happened throughout this undertaking. They have grown personally, interpersonally, and professionally on this journey. Unforeseeably, the intimidating door of SBM before them indeed is the key that unlocks the best version of teachers. Finally, this journey has lived up to that line of the song, “What does not kill you makes you stronger, stand a little taller; what does not kill you makes you a fighter, footsteps even lighter.”

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Princess Marynee V. Morga

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines

Johnny S. Bantulo

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines